

**NOAA Coastal Services Center Gulf of Mexico Alliance
Grantees Final Report**

DISL Number: 2302JD-JSU-01

Grantee: Jackson State University

Project: Website for Aquatic Plants and their Habitats of the Mississippi Coast

Period: October 1, 2009 through June 30, 2010

Date July 9, 2010

Project Summary Report:

This project involved environmental science majoring graduate students and undergraduate students of Jackson State University and a high school student of Rankin County. These students participate in: in-class workshops on coastal wetland habitats and aquatic plants of the Gulf coast; field work to conduct inventory of aquatic plants of the Mississippi coast and characterize their habitats; collection and cataloguing of photography and specimens of the plants; and development of field guide website/hardcopy book for aquatic plants and their habitats of Mississippi. This project complements a recently completed project of the PI funded by MS-AL Sea Grant Consortium (MASGC). Through the funds from GOMAE and MASGC, the students and the PI have been collecting specimens and information of over 115s' aquatic plants that grow in coastal Mississippi.

Project Activity Report:

The objective of this project was to develop a field guide website for aquatic plants of the Mississippi coast. The state of Mississippi has extensive inland and coastal wetlands and contains one of the most well-preserved, unmodified river basins of the United States: the Pascagoula River Basin. Nevertheless, there are few aquatic plant guide materials that exclusively address and discuss Mississippi aquatic plants. This website was developed based on field surveys conducted from spring 2007 through spring 2010. The field surveys were conducted in various areas along the Mississippi Coast, including Pascagoula River, Pearl River, Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve, Belle Fontaine Beach, Biloxi Bay, and beaches and wetland areas along Gulfport, Biloxi, Ocean Springs, Pascagoula, and Moss Point.

The procedures included pre-surveying for site selection, training student assistants, planning for field sampling time/frequency, field trips to the sites to take photography and to collect plant samples for permanent press or preserved specimens, editing of the photographs, the website development, layout/editing, and the launching of the website. Several people participated in the project by field guiding, plant identifying, reviewing, editing, and designing the website. JSU graduate/undergraduate students as well as a high school student assisted the projects by participating in the field work, sorting the specimens, and other laboratory and editorial work.

During the period from Oct 09 to Jun 2010, seven JSU students have participated in surveying aquatic plants and habitats in coastal Mississippi including, but not limited to Pearl River basin,

Pascagoula River, Back Bay of Biloxi, Gulf Island National Seashore, and Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve. Additional four students participated in compiling specimens and photographs to develop a field guide website and a fieldguide book.

From Aug 25 to Dec 10, 2009, the project involved the students enrolled in ENV 803, Wetland Ecology, taught by the PI, J. Cho. The students visited and surveyed local habitats of freshwater swamp, freshwater marsh, oligohaline tidal marsh, salt marsh, and estuaries through five field trips during this semester. The following areas are the places visited and surveyed: Cypress-Tupelo swamp along Natchez Trace, river bend of Pearl River, Lake Pontchartrain in Lacombe, LA, Belle Fontaine Beach, Gulf Coast Research Laboratory in Ocean Springs, Gulf Island National Seashore, various wetland habitats in Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve (NERR), and Franklin Creek. The tours at Grand Bay NERR were hosted by Jay McIlwain and Jennifer Buchanan.

Resulting Impact and Outcomes:

The final outcome of the project include a website (jcho.masgc.org) and a book of aquatic plants of the Mississippi coast that covered more than 100 species of free-floating, submerged, floating-leaved, and emergent plants. In order to minimize overlaps with other existing plant guide resources, the original plan for this website was to include only obligate wetland vascular plants that require persistent standing waters to survive, thrive, and reproduce and that strictly occur in Mississippi coastal areas. While the criteria have been kept when selecting plants for this book, a few exceptions were allowed to include *Ricciacarpus natans* (a Bryophyte that grows on the water surface), species within a genus (i.e. *Eleocharis*, *Juncus*) that contains both aquatic and facultative wetland species, and seagrasses that have been recorded in previous studies, but are lost or reduced significantly in Mississippi (i.e. *Syringodium*, *Halophila*, and *Thalassia*).

In Aug 2009, the website that contains information on more than 100 aquatic plants was officially launched and made available to the public. 100 hard copy field guide books were printed and distributed numerous extension and research organizations upon requests. A press was released to advertise the website and the book (<http://masgc.org/page.asp?id=439>). On Feb 18th, 2010, the website information was updated to include the contact information for the author, names of the editors and the contributors, and the funding agencies' information. In Jul 2010, the following 16 new species are being added to the list in the website: *Baccharis halmifolia*, *Batis maritima*, *Eleocharis baldwinii*, *Eleocharis palustris*, *Heteranthera dubia*, *Hydrilla verticillata*, *Iva frutescens*, *Myrica cerifera*, *Myriophyllum spicatum*, *Orontium aquaticum*, *Peltandra virginica*, *Polygonum punctatum*, *Potamogeton crispus*, *Sagittaria graminea* ssp. *Platyphylla*, *Utricularia radiata*, *Zizania aquatica*.

As stated above, this project provided several JSU students with field research experiences in coastal habitat characterization and aquatic plant species identification in the Mississippi coast. Jackson State University has master's and Ph.D. programs in Environmental Science which has produced significant number of scientists and educators. However, most of the students did not have opportunities to experience local coastal environments through field studies. Therefore, the project is directly related to the 3rd priority issue that the five U.S. Gulf States identified: Identification and Characterization of Gulf Habitats. This project falls under the following GOMA Environmental Education Actions: ED-3 Actions 1, 2, and 3.

The following is the list of JSU/high school students participated in the project.

Name	Classification	Origin/Race	Current Status/Role in the Project
------	----------------	-------------	------------------------------------

Gregory Jones	Post M.S. Student/Environmental Science	American/Black	Field surveys
Stephen Kishinhi	Ph.D. Student/Environmental Science	African/Black	Field surveys
Catherine Thomas	Ph.D. Student/Environmental Science	American/Black	Field surveys
Cristina Nica	Ph.D. Student/Environmental Science	European/White	Working on dissertation research on seagrass habitat modeling/ Field surveys
Philemon Kirui	Ph.D. Student/Environmental Science	African/Black	Working on dissertation research on hyperspectral feature selection for underwater objects for improved classification/ Field surveys
Marvin Washington	M.S. Student/Mathematics	African/Black	Participated field surveys in Spring 09 Working on M.S. thesis project: mathematical modeling of remotely sensed data for underwater habitats
Tereza Nevosadova	M.S. Student/Science Teaching	European/White	Participated in field guide website/book development. Graduated with M.S. in Science Teaching in Aug 2009
Yvonne Sanders	Undergraduate students/Social Studies	American/Black	Participated in field guide website/book development
Harene Natarajan	Undergraduate students/Physics	Asian/Indian	Participated in field guide website/book development
James Garner	Ph.D. Student/Environmental Science	American/White	Working on dissertation research on seagrass habitat modeling/ Field surveys and Data compiling
Annie Lu	High School Student	American/Asian	Participated in field guide website/book development Data compiling

Publications:

1. Cho, H.J. 2009. <http://jcho.masgc.org/> *Website of Aquatic Plants of the Mississippi Coast*. (website)
2. Cho, H.J. (Ed.) and others. 2009. *Aquatic Plants of the Mississippi Coast*. Jackson, MS. Pp.136. (Book)

Other related publications during the funding period (* indicates student authors)

3. Cho, H.J., P. Biber, M. Poirrier, and J. Garner*. (Accepted). Aquatic plants of Mississippi coastal river systems. *Journal of Mississippi Academy of Sciences*
4. Lu, D* and Cho, H.J. (in press). An improved water-depth correction algorithm for seagrass mapping using hyperspectral data. *Remote Sensing Letters*.
5. J. Watkins* and Cho, H.J. (Accepted). Seasonal and spatial variations of macrobenthic invertebrates in three Mississippi Gulf Coast bayous. *Journal of Mississippi Academy of Sciences*.
6. Cho, H.J. and P. Biber. 2010. Seed Propagation Protocol for Wigeongrass (*Ruppia maritima* L.) (Mississippi). *Ecological Restoration* 28(2): 135-137.
7. Cho, H.J. and D. Lu. 2010. A water-depth correction algorithm for submerged vegetation spectra. *Remote Sensing Letters* 1(1): 29-35.
8. Cho, H.J., P. Biber, and C. Nica*. 2009. The Rise of *Ruppia* in Seagrass Beds: Changes in coastal environment and research needs. Chapter (In) *Handbook on Environmental Quality* (Eds.) Evan K. Drury and Tylor S. Pridgen. Nova Science Publishers, Inc. Hauppauge, NY. (ISBN: 978-1-60741-420-9).
9. Cho, H.J. and C. Nica*. 2009. A study of seagrass at Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve, Mississippi. *Proceedings of the 2009 MS Water Resource Conference* 114-117.
10. Cho, H.J., D. Lu*, and M. Washington*. 2009. Water correction algorithm application for underwater vegetation signal improvement. *Proceedings of the 2009 MS Water Resource Conference* 152-155.
11. Cho, H.J. and Y.L. Sanders*. 2009. Note on Organic Dormancy of Estuarine *Ruppia maritima* seeds. *Hydrobiologia* 617: 197-201.
12. Shayron Nicoles*, Hyunju Kim, Ali A. Humos, and Hyun Jung Cho. 2009. A Performance Evaluation on Discrete Cosine Transform and Wavelet-based Compression Methods for Remote Sensing Images based on Image Content. *Proceedings of the 2009 Geoinformatics*.

What problems (or sources of error) were encountered, if any? NA

If a problem was encountered, what action was taken to correct it?

Is the project work on schedule?

Yes, but a 3 month- no cost extension was requested to include additional plants to the website by June 2010. The extension was approved.

Monitoring and Maintenance Activities

The participating students were trained for plant/habitat identifications and field safety prior to field trips, supervised and monitored by the project manager in the field and laboratory. The field trips have been and will continue to be scheduled to ensure to depict the important phenological events of the plants. Plant identification was done rigorously through the trained students using numerous reference materials and again in the laboratory using microscopes. When necessary, the photos and specimens were sent to external experts for further clarification. Three external advisory people were invited to review and serve as co-editors of the project outcomes.

Community Involvement

The following people contributed to the book development by either serving as a field guide or a reviewer of the materials: Patrick Biber and JD Caldwell at Gulf Coast Research Laboratory; James T. Blocker at the Nature Conservancy; Jennifer Buchanan and Jay McIlwain at Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve; Jeff Clark at Department of Marine Resources; Michael Poirrier at University of New Orleans, and Robert Mohlenbrock at Biotic Consultants, Inc.

The tours at Grand Bay NERR for JSU students were hosted by Jay McIlwain and Jennifer Buchanan.

Mississippi-Alabama Sea Grant Consortium (MASGC) is hosting the website. Dr. Dmitri Sobolev, Assistant Professor at University of Houston at Victoria helped design the website. John Grigsby at MASGC is in charge of the website maintenance.

Outreach Activities

Described above (in the section Progress and Results)

Supporting Materials

- Website: jcho.masgc.org
- Book: I have submitted a copy to the DISL.
- Press Release: <http://masgc.org/page.asp?id=439>
- Photos (Students of Wetland Ecology Course surveying a cypress-tupelo swamp on Sept 5, 2009): additional photos of the plants that are being added to the website are also included as an attachment.

Wetland Ecology Class at a cypress swamp

Wetland Ecology Class at an oligohaline estuary and marsh, Lake Pontchartrain

At Gulf Island National Seashore

in Ocean Springs

Welcome to the Mississippi Aquatic Plants Website - Windows Internet Explorer

http://jcho.masgc.org/

File Edit View Favorites Tools Help

Welcome to the Mississippi Aquatic Plants Website

Growth Forms Habitats *free-floating* *submerged* *floating-leaved* *emergent*

Return to Main Full Gallery *sedges* *grasses* *rushes* *trees and bushes* Links

Welcome to the Mississippi Aquatic Plants Website

On the left is our gallery; use it for navigating the site. Clicking a plant name or picture brings up a page dedicated to that plant; selecting a picture on the page retrieves a high-resolution image (where available - warning, large download!) The gallery can be sorted according to plant's common or scientific (Latin) name by clicking links at the top. You can browse the entire gallery or select a sub-gallery at the top. Alternatively, you can familiarize yourself with various aquatic plants habitats by clicking appropriate link.

Note for users

The state of Mississippi has extensive inland and coastal wetlands and contains one of the most well-preserved, unmodified river basins of the U.S., the Pascagoula River Basin. Nevertheless, there are few aquatic plant websites that address and discuss exclusively the Mississippi aquatic plants. This website was developed based on field surveys conducted spring 2007 through spring 2009. The field surveys were conducted in various areas along the Mississippi Coast, including Pascagoula River, Pearl River, Grand Bay National Estuarine Research Reserve & Refuge, Belle Fontaine Beach, Biloxi Bay, beaches and wetland areas along Gulfport, Biloxi, Ocean Springs, and Pascagoula, and Moss Point.

Photos and text - H. J. Cho, Jackson State University. Web design - D. Sobolev, University of Houston-Victoria

start Internet Explorer Application Microsoft Office ... EN 16:58

Front page of the website